

Electrochemical and Viscous Properties of Synthetic Humic Acids

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Synthetic humic acids have been prepared from each of catechol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, vanillin, glucose and gallic acid with or without glycine as the source of nitrogen by simple air oxidation in 0.5*N* sodium hydroxide solution at 32° in the presence of different catalytic surfaces, e.g., clay, sand and silt fractions of soil. After about one month of air oxidation, the humus formed was separated with 0.5*N* sodium carbonate solution by centrifugation from which humic acids were precipitated with hydrochloric acid at pH 2–3. They were purified by repeating the processes of dissolution and precipitation and finally by dialysis and electro dialysis. Conductometric, potentiometric and viscosity studies of the solutions of the synthetic humic acids reveal their polyelectrolytic nature. Features of titration curves, mainly the conductometric ones, of humic acids with or without nitrogen in their molecules were compared amongst themselves and with those of the monomers, from which the nature of the functional groups could be suggested. The similarity of the behaviour of the synthetic humic acids with their natural counterparts was clearly noticeable, suggesting a similar mechanism of formation of the latter.

The dark organic matter in soil has attracted the attention of chemists for more than a century but, despite intensive investigations by many workers, knowledge of the nature of this material is still very limited. Part of the difficulty is that the humic material in soil is mixed with many substances derived from decomposing plants and animals, which complicate the isolation and purification of the humic materials.

Investigations concerned with the isolation and fractionation of humic material have been well summarized by Waksman¹ and Kononova². The evaluation of the various extracts and of fractionation methods has been handicapped by the lack of suitable means of characterizing the products obtained. Most workers have recognized four fractions, the so-called fulvic, humic and humatmelanic acids which can be extracted fairly readily in basic media, and the more or less insoluble residual material termed humin. Elemental analysis of these fractions differs somewhat but it is widely assumed that the substances which form the different fractions are fundamentally similar and differ primarily in their degree of polymerization and perhaps oxidation. It is not quite correct to assume that these fractions are chemically homogeneous. In fact, several groups of substances such as carbohydrates and protein substances have been isolated in some of these fractions. Most of the work on humus has been concentrated on the humic acid fraction which, because of its solubility in alkalis and insolubility in acids, alcohol and ether, can be readily extracted and purified. Chemical investigations have led to the widely accepted view that humic acids are heteropoly condensates of phenolic substances with or without the participation of amino acids². Attempts to identify the units which form the condensate have been hampered by the absence of degradation procedures that yield monomers with unchanged substitution

1. S. A. Waksman, 'Humus', Bailliere, Tindal and Cox, London, 1936.
2. M. M. Kononova, Soil organic matter, Pergamon Press 1961.

patterns and intact carbon side chains. There is also little information on the oxygen of the contributing units and their mode of linkage. Despite many attempts no satisfactory methods have been described that enable humic acids from different sources to be distinguished from each other. Soil humic acids are polybasic, containing functional groups like carboxyl, hydroxyl (both phenolic and alcoholic, the former predominating), enolic, primary amino and imino groups. The problem of identifying the functional groups and of determining their amount and relative orientation in a polyfunctional macromolecule is one of great theoretical and practical interest.

Attempts from several directions are possible for this purpose. Thus, Halle³, Broadbent and Bradford⁴, Forsyth⁵ have suggested the possibility of determining the phenolic and carboxyl group by the usual method of methylation with dimethyl sulphate and diazomethane. The details are given in their publications.

Electrometric methods involving potentiometric and conductometric titrations have been followed in these investigations and the interpretations of the results are somewhat as follows. The amount of alkali required to titrate humic acid up to pH 7.0 is recognised as that due to -COOH group and that above this pH due to the phenolic group, provided, of course, that these are the only two acid groups involved. Some workers believe that the transition pH is 8.2 instead of 7.0, and hence a certain degree of empiricity comes into the choice of this pH. The conditions under which identification of acid groups of polybasic acids is possible from the shape of the potentiometric titration curves with alkalis have been thoroughly discussed by Auerbach and Smolczyk⁶ and Sims and Peters⁷.

Conductometric titrations are also quite informative as regards the functional groups. Breaks in the titration curves and the respective slopes enable us to identify these groups. For both these techniques it is, however, necessary to have a knowledge of the features of some model substances.

Physico-chemical properties of synthetic humic acids prepared from catechol, hydroquinone and glucose in the solution have already been studied, which have enabled characterisation of the products and showed similarity in behaviour with the naturally occurring substances⁸. Natural humic acids are believed to be formed by almost similar oxidation and condensation reactions except that they take place in presence of solid phase in the form of clay, silt and sand and other inorganic and organic (particularly bacterial or other enzymes) constituents of the soil. It is plausible that the inorganic materials provide catalytic surface for such condensation and oxidation reactions. The synthetic reactions leading to the formation of humic acids were, therefore, carried out in presence of sand, silt and clay fractions isolated from the soil. The details are given below.

3. R. Halle, *Brennstoffchem.*, 1935, **16**, 361.
4. F. E. Broadbent and G. R. Bradford, *Soil. Sci.*, 1952, **74**, 447.
5. W. G. C. Forsyth, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1947, **37**, 132.
6. F. R. Auerbach and E. Smolczyk, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1924, **110**, 65.
7. D. Sims and L. Peters, *Nature*, 1957, **108**, 805.
8. K. B. Roy. Doctorate Thesis, 1965. University of Calcutta. (Unpublished).

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay, sand and silt fractions were separated from Darjeeling and Chinsura soil (West Bengal) samples by the usual method and then freed each fraction from adhering organic matter by hydrogen peroxide treatment. Humus was prepared in presence of the above cleaned soil separates using catechol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, vanillin, glucose and gallic acid as monomers with and without glycine as the source of nitrogen, by simple air oxidation over about a month of 0.5*N* sodium hydroxide solution. After this period humus was extracted with 0.5*N* sodium carbonate solution and the supernatant was separated from the residue (rejected) by decantation and filtration. From the filtrate humic acids were precipitated by acidification with hydrochloric acid to *pH* 2–3. The precipitate separated from the supernatant liquid by centrifugation and the clear filtrate (fulvic acids) was collected. The precipitate was redissolved in alkali, filtered and reprecipitated. This operation was repeated thrice. The precipitate was finally washed several times with 0.1*N* hydrochloric acid and freed from electrolytes by water dialysis followed by mild electro dialysis. The humic acid thus obtained in aqueous suspension is known as crude humic acid, and was preserved in pyrex flask. In order to separate alcohol soluble part (i.e., hymatomelanic acid) from this crude product, suitable aliquots of the suspension were dried in vacuum and the dried material refluxed in ethanol till the alcohol was colourless. The ethanol insoluble fraction containing humic acid was redissolved in alkali and precipitated with hydrochloric acid at *pH* 2–3. The precipitate was purified by washing and dialysis in the same manner as the crude humic acid.

The crude humic acids prepared from catechol, hydroquinone, vanillin, gallic acid and glucose are black shining particles but the resorcinol humic acid is red in colour. The natural humic acids are generally brown, grey or red in colour. Drying has an interesting effect on the solubility and dispersion properties of the different fractions of the humic acids. Thus, dried crude glucose humic acid easily disperses in water but the purified dried fraction does not, just as it is so for the crude soil humic acid⁹. Like the latter the crude dried humic acids from phenols do not disperse in water. The fractionation of hymatomelanic from humic acids with the aid of alcohol in nowadays seldom applied because reflux with alcohol may change the properties of humic acid and since the yield of hymatomelanic acid from some of the synthetic polymerized products was found to be very small, most of the studies on the preparations have been carried out with the crude humic acid.

The conductometric titrations were carried out with a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge using a 1000-cycle oscillator at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The titrations were carried out continuously with sodium and barium hydroxides in a cell of comparatively low cell constant.

The potentiometric titrations were done with the help of a Cambridge *pH* meter. Potentiometric titrations were carried out both by continuous and discontinuous procedures and in the absence and presence of electrolytes.

The viscosity of the sodium salts of the suspensions of humic acids was conveniently measured instead of those of humic acids themselves, both in presence and absence of sodium

chloride. The viscosity measurements were done with the help of a capillary viscometer of the Cannon-Fenske type having a relatively high flow time. All the viscosity measurements were done in a water thermostat maintained at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ by Aminco-mercury thermostat operating in conjunction with an electronic relay system.

The sodium salts were prepared by adding sodium hydroxide to pH 8.0 to electro-dialysed suspension of humic acid. The sodium humate thus formed was concentrated and precipitated with alcohol-acetone or ether-acetone mixture, centrifuged and washed several times with 95% neutral alcohol. The salt was finally dried in vacuum at 85° and preserved in a desiccator. Solutions of known concentration were prepared from this stock sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conductometric titration which gave somewhat better information about the functional groups and enabled the equivalent point to be determined with greater accuracy are discussed first, and the graphs are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The legends given there indicate

Fig. 1.—Conductometric titration of catechol, hydroquinone and Resorcinol humic acid with NaOH.

Fig. 2.—Conductometric titration of humic acids containing nitrogen with NaOH.

the nature and source of the humic acids and titrants. The curves having the general features of weak acids show a single break indicating a monobasic behaviour of these humic acids. This is similar to the findings of van Dijk¹⁰ who worked with synthetic humic acids from hydroquinone and pyrocatechol. Humic acids prepared in presence of glycine when titrated with barium hydroxide⁺ and sodium hydroxide show an initial lowering in conductance.

The preparations of humic acids in absence of glycine show slightly different features in their titration curves. Those with baryta show two breaks but they are less sharp and the initial marked drop is conspicuously absent. The titration curves of these humic acids with sodium hydroxide show, unlike those of barium hydroxide, a single break which is marked by a greater slope corresponding to addition of about 375 and 285 m.e./100 g. of the alkali for catechol and hydroquinone humic acids respectively (Fig. 1). The humic acid preparations in presence of glycine, however, show a slight difference in the conductometric titrations from those without glycine. The difference is mainly in the initial portions of the curves. For instance, titrations with barium hydroxide⁺ and sodium hydroxide show an initial lowering, the extent of which varies with the nature of the preparations and the alkali. The preparations are supposed to be otherwise similar except perhaps in their contents of nitrogen. The extent to which glycine has reacted with the products of polymerisation and the manner in which this has been distributed in the different fractions will determine the content of nitrogen. Since these particular humic acid preparations contains nitrogen are characterised by an initial lowering, whereas those without nitrogen do not show any such lowering, like fulvic acids, it has been guessed that this may be due to the free -COOH of the glycine residues. Qualitatively, humic acid hydrolysates containing nitrogen do show the presence of glycine (by paper chromatography) in varying amounts.

In spite of the similarity in the titration curves with the two alkalies mentioned above, certain characteristic differences are clearly noticeable. For example, the initial lowering is sharper in the sodium hydroxide titration curves than those with barium hydroxide.

In order to find out the similarity and dissimilarity of the original monomer with the polymerized humic acids studied above the conductometric titrations of catechol, hydroquinone and gallic acid in aqueous solutions have been performed with sodium and barium hydroxides⁺. (Fig. 3). The titration curves are characterised in general by weak breaks compared with those of the corresponding humic acids. The single breaks in the titrations of catechol and hydroquinone correspond to the neutralization of the two phenolic hydroxyl groups. The gallic acid titration curve shows a small initial lowering and one break corresponding to³neutralisation of the -COOH group and another to that of the phenolic hydroxyl groups. From the conductometric titration curves of catechol, hydroquinone and gallic acid with sodium and barium hydroxides it may be concluded that if any free carboxyl group

⁺ The barium hydroxide titration curves show a long initial flat run till the end point. Being otherwise similar to the sodium hydroxide curve they are omitted.

10. H. Van Dijk. *Sci. Proc. Royal Dub. Soc.*, 1960, 1, Series A, 163.

is present in the acidic substance, an initial drop in conductance will be noticed, whereas if it contains only phenolic hydroxyls then the conductance will increase from the beginning of titration.

Fig. 3.—Conductometric titration of catechol, hydroquinone and gallic acid with NaOH.

The conductometric titration curves of catechol, hydroquinone and resorcinol humic acids containing no nitrogen with sodium and barium hydroxides are very similar in nature to those of the corresponding monomers.

The conductometric titration curves of the humic acids containing nitrogen with sodium and barium hydroxides are very similar in nature to that of gallic acid with these bases suggesting the presence of $-\text{COOH}$ groups. It is believed that the glycine residue attached to the polymer contributes to the $-\text{COOH}$ group.

TABLE I

Substance	B.e.c.(m.e.) Conductometric		Concentration %	Specific	Specific
	NaOH	Ba(OH) ₂		Conductance at $\alpha = 0$	Conductance at $\alpha = 1$
				mho $\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^5$	mho $\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^5$
Catechol-H	275	272	.027	1.5	.71
Hydroquinone-H	285	285	.038	1.24	5.27
Resorcinol-H	820	740	.012		
Catechol-H(N)	225	293	.068	3.41	6.20
Hydroquinone-H(N)	400	420	.031	2.48	8.99
Resorcinol-H(N)	416	380	.0412	2.48	5.89
Vanillin-H(N)	435	432	.089	1.70	7.28
Glucose-H(N)	665	565	.0311	1.33	.775
Gallic-H(N)	540	530	.0211	3.87	8.83

+ See footnote on page 000.

+ Those with barium hydroxide have got similar features, but vary only in shape. They have, therefore, been omitted.

The base exchange capacities of the different humic acid preparations lie in the range of 225 to 820 m.e. whereas for the soil humic acid⁹ they are in the range of 500 to 700 m.e. The specific conductances at the equivalence points (i.e., of the sodium humate solution) vary from 5.27 to 8.99×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 30°, whereas the corresponding values for soil humic acid⁹ lie at a somewhat higher range, viz., 25.0 to 37.0×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 30°.

The potentiometric titration curves with sodium hydroxide* are shown in Fig. 4. The end points have been more accurately located from the differential curves (not shown). The discontinuous titrations owing to prolonged reaction yield in general higher values of acid equivalence than those by continuous titrations. A comparison of the total acidity and equivalent weight determined by both the conductometric and potentiometric methods is shown in Tables I and II respectively. From these results it will be seen that the total acidities of the synthetic products are less when measured by the potentiometric than by the conductometric method.

Fig. 4.—Potentiometric titration of humic acids containing nitrogen with NaOH.

TABLE II

Substance	B.e.c.(m.e.) Potentiometric		pK_a		pK_{int}	
	in absence of NaCl	in 0.5N NaCl	in absence of NaCl	in 0.5N NaCl	in absence of NaCl	in 0.5N NaCl
Catechol-H(N)	264	328	6.0	4.9	5.2	3.2
Hydroquinone-H(N)	347	415	6.1	5.6	5.7	4.7
Resorcinol-H(N)	344	480	6.3	4.5	5.7	3.7
Vanillin-H(N)	600	670	6.60	5.8	6.5	5.2
Glucose-H(N)	440	520	6.1	5.3	5.80	4.2
Gallic-H(N)	256	305	6.40	5.6	6.00	4.7

* Those with barium hydroxide have got similar features but vary only in shape. They have, therefore, been omitted.

The apparent pK_{ar} values were determined from the pH titration curves at 50% neutralisation. The apparent pK_{ar} values (Table II) in absence of electrolytes range from 6.0 to 6.6. If these are not treated as very weak acids an approximate pK_{ar} can be obtained from the equation $pH = 1/2 pK_{ar} - 1/2 \log c$, by plotting pH against $-\log c$ and finding out the pH corresponding to $-\log c = 0$. These values are in fair agreement with those obtained from potentiometric curves. The addition of salt (0.5 *N* sodium chloride) lowers the pK_{ar} for soil humic acids¹¹ from 5.4 to 6.4.

The pK_{int} values can be calculated from the equation¹²

$$\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} - pH = pK_{int} - 0.868 \alpha \omega \bar{Z}$$

where $\alpha = \bar{r}/n$, \bar{r} is the average number of H^+ ions dissociated per macromolecule calculated in the present case as the ratio of the m.e. of base added to the b.e.c. or total acidity, n is the average total numbers of such dissociable protons per molecule; \bar{Z} is the net average charge on the molecule and ω is the electrostatic interaction factor. Thus, plotting $\left(pH - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right)$ against α , pK_{int} will be found out as the intercept at $\alpha = 0$, since $Z = 0$ when $\alpha = 0$ (See Fig. 5*). It is to be noted from the results shown in Table II that the pK_{int} lies between

Fig. 5.— pK_{int} of humic acids containing nitrogen.

5.2 and 6.5. On the addition of sodium chloride the pH values of the humic acid suspensions as well as the values of pK_{int} are lowered. pK_{int} becomes closer to 4.7 which is that of the carboxyl group. In presence of sodium chloride the polyelectrolytic humic acids are likely to be coiled, as a result some of the $-COOH$ and $-OH$ groups may be prevented from registering their effects on the glass electrode. Consequently, the pH ought to have been raised instead of getting lowered. However, Na^+ because of its high concentration will exchange

11. A. E. Martin and R. Reeve, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1958, **9**, 89.

12. C. Tanford. *Physical Chemistry of Macromolecules*, John Wiley and Sons Inc. 1962.

* The graphs in presence of 0.5*N* sodium chloride are similar and hence not given here. The pK_{int} calculated from the graphs are, however, given in Table II.

bound H^+ ions belonging both to the $-COOH$ and $-OH$ groups. These H^+ ions will, therefore, cause a lowering of pH . Moreover, coiling would tend to reduce the volume available for the exchanged H^+ ions and hence increase the H^+ ion concentration. The two processes which would lower the pH obviously override the effect of coiling, tending to raise it and hence a final lowering of pH is observed with the addition of sodium chloride. It is further to be noted that in some cases the curves in absence of the salt are not linear, while in its presence they are linear. The nonlinearity only means that ω is not constant and since

$$\omega = \frac{3e^2}{5DR_e} (1 + 0.6KR_e + 0.4K^2R_e^2) \quad \dots (2)$$

where R_e = radius of the equivalent hydrodynamic sphere, it is evident that in absence of salt R_e is not constant. This conclusion is entirely in accord with the polyelectrolyte character of humic acids⁸ (see also the viscosity behaviour discussed below).

The polyelectrolytic character of natural peat humic acid has been demonstrated by Pirtet *et al.*¹³. The presence of charged groups along the chain makes polyelectrolytes remarkably different from other types of polymers. The most interesting property which distinguishes polyelectrolytes from other type of polymers is the way in which the reduced viscosity η_{sp}/c is dependent on concentration. For a neutral macromolecule in solution the reduced viscosity usually decreases with decreasing concentration, while for a saltfree polyelectrolyte η_{sp}/c vs. c curve rises rapidly with diminishing concentration. In order to obviate the influence of charge, Fuoss and Cathers¹⁴ have suggested the following equation, from which $[\eta]$ can be evaluated by plotting $1/\eta_{sp}/c$ vs. \sqrt{c} .

$$\eta_{sp}/c = \frac{A}{1 + B\sqrt{c}} \quad \dots (3)$$

TABLE III

Substance	Salt free $[\eta]$ (ml/gm) (From Fuoss— Cathers plot)	0.1M NaCl $[\eta]$ (ml/gm)
Catechol-H(N)	29	6.0
Hydroquinone-H(N)	23	4.9
Resorcinol-H(N)	18	10.0
Vanillin-H(N)	60	6.3
Glucose-H(N)	60	4.2
Gallic-H(N)	28	10.0

The values of intrinsic viscosity obtained by extrapolation according to Fuoss-Cathers equation to zero concentration of the salt free sodium humate lie in the range of 18 to

13. E. L. Pirtet, R. G. White, H. C. Walter, Jr. and A. J. Madden, Jr., *Sci. Proc. Royal. Dub. Soc.*, 1960, 1, Series A, 69.
14. R. N. Fuoss and C. I. Cathers, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1949, 4, 97.

60 ml./gm. For the soil humic acid $[\eta]$ is about 15.4 ml./gm. at 35°. The results of viscosity measurements are shown in Figs. 6, 7 and 8. The typical behaviour of polyelectrolytes

Fig. 6.—Viscosity study of humic acids containing nitrogen as Na salt at 35°.

Fig. 7.—Reciprocal plot of viscosity study of Na humate at 35°.

is displayed by all the curves. The addition of 0.1 N sodium chloride suppresses the polyelectrolyte nature and η_{sp}/c vs. c graph becomes linear enabling extrapolation and evaluation of the intrinsic viscosity. The values of the latter are given in Table III and are found to lie in the range of 4.2 to 10 ml./gm. By comparison $[\eta]$ for a humic acid isolated from a black cotton soil is 2.1 ml./gm. at 35°.⁹

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Fig. 8.—Viscosity study of humic acids containing nitrogen as Na salt in 0.1N NaCl at 35°.

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